

An Approach for Social-Distance Preserving Location-Aware Recommender Systems: A Use Case in a Hospital Environment

Marcos Caballero¹[0009-0002-0507-4503], María del Carmen Rodríguez-Hernández¹[0000-0002-0062-9525], Raúl Parada²[0000-0002-1899-5881], Sergio Ilarri³[0000-0002-7073-219X], Raquel Trillo-Lado³[0000-0002-7641-1864], Ramón Hermoso⁴[0000-0002-1517-2820], and Óscar J. Rubio⁵[0000-0001-9680-5855]

¹ Technological Institute of Aragón (ITA), María de Luna 7-8, Zaragoza, Spain
{[mcaballero](mailto:mcaballero@itainnova.es), [mcrodriguez](mailto:mcrodriguez@itainnova.es)}@itainnova.es

² Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC/CERCA), Av. Carl Friedrich Gauss 7, Castelldefels, Barcelona, Spain
rparada@cttc.cat

³ I3A, Universidad de Zaragoza, María de Luna 1, Zaragoza, Spain
{[silarri](mailto:silarri@unizar.es), [raqueltl](mailto:raqueltl@unizar.es)}@unizar.es

⁴ Universidad de Zaragoza, Violante de Hungría 23, Zaragoza, Spain
{[rhermoso](mailto:rhermoso@unizar.es)}@unizar.es

⁵ Imascono Company, Josefa Amar y Borbón 10, Zaragoza, Spain
oscar@imascono.com

Abstract. Currently, the volume of geo-referenced data is rapidly expanding, and users frequently show interest in nearby items. Consequently, Location-Aware Recommender Systems (LARS) have garnered considerable attention from the research community in recent years. However, these systems are not ideally suited for situations where social distancing is crucial for people’s safety, such as during the COVID-19 pandemic.

In this paper, we study this problem through a use case scenario: recommending items (e.g., informative posters, medical videos, and location signals) for observation during an open-door hospital visit. We propose an approach for Side-LARS (SoCial-Distance prEserving LARS), a trajectory and user-based collaborative filtering algorithm, that incorporates location data, user behaviors and social distancing constraints to provide personalized recommendations. Additionally, to be able to evaluate our approach, we extend the capabilities of a synthetic recommendation dataset generator called AUTO-DataGenCARS+, to generate implicit ratings and user behaviors, enabling us to evaluate Side-LARS using a mixed scenario with both real and synthetic datasets. The experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposal in maintaining social distancing while providing personalized recommendations. Furthermore, the practical utility of AUTO-DataGenCARS+ in real-world use-case scenario evaluations is highlighted.

Keywords: Location-Aware Recommender Systems · Social distance · Implicit ratings · Synthetic dataset generation.

1 Introduction

In recent years, Location-Aware Recommender Systems (LARS) have garnered significant interest due to their ability to consider spatial features (e.g., locations) of users and/or items for the computation of suitable recommendations. The emergence of LARS is attributed to users' preference for nearby items, due to the reduced effort required to access items closer to their physical location. In general, LARS can be considered an extension of traditional recommender systems, and an important subset of Context-Aware Recommender Systems (CARS) [5, 18], that exploit the location as a contextual attribute.

The emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the essential need for social distancing, particularly in public areas such as hospitals, where guiding visitors effectively can significantly impact the overall experience and safety. Nowadays, traditional LARS are inadequate in scenarios where physical distancing is crucial. This gap demands novel solutions to adapt LARS in a way that they not only offer relevant recommendations but also ensure the safety of individuals by preserving the social distance, which we call *Side-LARS (Social-Distance prEserving LARS)*. This paper aims to address this issue, proposing a location-aware recommender system designed to offer a personalized route of items to users, preserving the social distances among users. The proposed system operates on a push-based model, automatically updating recommendations based on the user's current location, item locations, and user behaviors, including social distancing constraints. This approach is contextualized through a use case scenario in a hospital environment, where the system recommends trajectories through items (e.g., informative posters, medical videos, and location signals) during an open-door hospital visit. Another key challenge in working on LARS is the proper evaluation of the performance of recommender systems in various scenarios, to demonstrate their suitability. In order to address this issue, we extend and employ the AUTO-DataGenCARS+ generator [15] to create a hybrid dataset, blending synthetic and real data, for assessing our recommendation approach.

The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows: 1) the development of an approach for Side-LARS, a pioneering proposal that harmonizes personalized recommendations with social distancing constraints; 2) an extension of a synthetic recommendation dataset generator to support the generation of implicit ratings and user behaviors, facilitating the evaluation of Side-LARS in a mixed scenario using both real and synthetic datasets; and 3) an experimental evaluation that shows the benefits of the proposal. The structure of the rest of this paper is as follows. In Section 2, we present a literature review of location-aware recommender systems that suggest sequences of items to visit to users. In Section 3, we describe the methodology used to define the experimental scenario and the proposed recommender system. In Section 4, we present the experimental results, that show the benefits of the proposal. Finally, in Section 5, we present our conclusions and some prospective lines of future work.

2 Related Work

Location-aware recommender systems have gained significant attention due to their ability to enhance the user experience by incorporating geographical information into the recommendation process. These systems are particularly valuable in sectors where the location relevance is essential, such as in fields related to travel, hotel industry, and local services. They enhance the user satisfaction by offering relevant items, adapting dynamically to the user’s changing locations and immediate needs. In papers such as [?,8,23], the authors have deeply reviewed the existing literature on LARS, analyzing different approaches and their application domains. In this section, our review of the state of the art is focused on item trajectory recommendation approaches that incorporate location information, user behaviors and constraints to provide personalized recommendation in mobile environments.

There are some works that exploit information available in Location-Based Social Networks (LBSNs), where recommender systems use check-in data to identify the locations of potentially interesting places [7]. Social and geographical data are used to improve the recommendations of POIs (Points of Interest), based on the idea that people prefer places suggested by friends and similar users visit nearby locations. An example is CLoSe (Contextualized Location Sequence recommender) [4], which suggests POI sequences (e.g., for planning itineraries) using Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models. Besides, in [19], a hybrid location-aware recommender approach was introduced, which utilizes LSTM to discover user similarities based on social media posts and demographic information (obtained from LBSNs) and incorporates BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) [1] to predict and recommend a sequence of POIs; furthermore, it employs the DBSCAN clustering method [25] to identify regions of interest based on geographic coordinates. The evaluation results indicate that POIBERT outperforms other baseline algorithms. As a final example, an alternative approach was proposed in [26], based on the X-means method [21] and graph embedding to cluster users based on their coordinates by analyzing geo-spatial data published on LBSNs. This was motivated by the idea that people with similar travel patterns tend to have similar travel preferences. Consequently, the system recommends a POI itinerary to a user which is likely to be visited by another user from the same cluster.

On the other hand, some studies integrate real-time location data (obtained through GPS) to recommend personalized item trajectories that match the user’s preferences and current location. This approach not only improves the relevance of recommendations but also introduces a spatial dimension to the user experience, offering suggestions that are both contextually and geographically appropriate. For example, POIBERT [10] is a BERT language model adapted to recommend tour itineraries for tourists visiting unfamiliar cities. This recommender model is based on historical POI visit trajectories of similar tourists, taking into account time constraints; the evaluation results indicate that POIBERT outperforms other baseline algorithms. Recently, BTRec [9] has extended

the capabilities of the POIBERT model by incorporating additional demographic information about travelers (such as their cities and countries) into the training of the embedding model, in order to increase the accuracy of predictions. Another notable example is GeoSAN [16], a Geography-aware Sequential Recommender based on a Self-Attention Network. This system marks an important advancement in LARS, as it makes efficient use of geographic information and presents a novel approach to address data sparsity issues. It exploits a self-attention-based geography encoder, an importance sampling-based loss function and geography-aware negative samplers, enhancing the model’s ability to effectively use geographical information and improve the quality of recommendations. GeoSAN specializes in recommending the next location of POIs and services based on the user location and preferences. The algorithm’s effectiveness is demonstrated by its significant performance improvement over state-of-the-art sequential location recommenders in real-world datasets (Gowalla, Brightkite and Foursquare).

A key missing feature of the previous works is that they are not suitable in scenarios with health constraints that limit the mobility of users, as they can generate recommendations that violate those constraints and may represent a risk for a virus propagation. Thus, the COVID-19 pandemic has brought about significant changes in our daily lives, introducing social distancing as an essential aspect of how we utilize and offer services. As a consequence, it would be relevant to integrate social distancing constraints and crowd-awareness into recommender systems [17]. In this context, a pioneering example is the idea of Side-CARS (SoCial-Distance prEserving CARS), introduced in [13], but without proposing a specific solution to develop these kind of systems. As explained in [12], we consider the concept “social distance” from a general perspective, as in some scenarios the number of nearby people within an area could be more important than the direct physical distance between people. Based on these ideas, in this paper we develop a first solution, focused on the exploitation of location attributes. The importance of social distancing for route planning has also been emphasized in works such as [24, 3]. However, as far as we know, no other work in the literature has proposed an approach for Side-CARS or Side-LARS.

3 Methodology and Use Case

In this section, we describe the proposed methodology and a use case scenario that we will use to study and evaluate the proposed recommender system. More specifically, in Section 3.1, we present the proposed recommendation process, delving into the Side-LARS algorithm that utilizes real-time locations and social distances between users to suggest item trajectories. Finally, in Section 3.2, we detail the scenario of a hospital, considered as a use case, whose objective is to improve the visitors’ satisfaction.

3.1 Location-Aware Recommender Architecture

The architecture underlying the recommendation process is structured around a centralized architecture that prioritizes server-based computation. This struc-

ture, as depicted in Figure 1, is partitioned into three distinct layers: the *View Layer*, where users engage with the items within the *Environment*; the *Logic Layer*, which forms the computational heart of the system; and the *Data Layer*, where all necessary data are stored and managed. At the core of the Logic Layer resides the Side-LARS algorithm, a sophisticated component of the *Recommendation Engine* that takes real-time user locations and social distancing into account, delivering personalized item trajectories. This system is designed to dynamically update and adapt its recommendations as users navigate through the space.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the proposed Side-LARS recommender system.

The objective of the recommender system is to maximize the user satisfaction during a visit to a place containing items that can be watched. For this purpose, we have defined an approach for Side-LARS based on the post-filtering paradigm [2]. It is inspired by the approach presented in [22], which was extended by incorporating an additional constraint for social distancing [13]. An activity diagram of this algorithm is shown in Figure 2, providing a detailed overview of its components. Beforehand, it is assumed that all users are making use of the recommender system.

Fig. 2. Activity diagram presenting Side-LARS algorithm pipeline.

The algorithm begins by finding other users with similar preferences to the target user through *User-Based Collaborative Filtering (UBCF)*. Known ratings provided by these similar users are considered to estimate potential ratings that the target user might assign to different items. Based on these estimations, the top- k items (i.e., the k items with the best predicted ratings not yet seen by the user) are identified as potential candidate for recommendation. If there are not enough data for UBCF to provide results (cold start problem), then the k -nearest points of interest are collected as candidate items, using the *Nearest Point of Interest (NPOI)* strategy. Additionally, this issue could be mitigated by retaining the user identifier in an analytics cookie in the user’s app, or by implementing a login system that manages this identifier using a database, thus ensuring that users only experience the cold start during their initial interaction with the space. In the post-filtering phase, the resulting items are then reordered, if necessary, to minimize the distance the user will need to go through to access those items. The shortest path passing through all those k items is computed. After that, several circumstances could trigger a reevaluation of the recommendation process:

1. When the recommender system has a significant amount of new information stored (e.g., a good number of new ratings provided by users).
2. When the user is about to leave an area (e.g., a room in a building), and it is therefore convenient to check if there is any additional item in that area worth visiting at that moment.
3. When the user has significantly deviated from the recommended trajectory (e.g., because something not recommended attracted their attention).
4. When the recommendation algorithm fails to maintain social distance between users to prevent overcrowding.

Specifically, the social distancing constraint is applied to prevent overcrowding by enforcing a minimum Euclidean distance threshold between the recommended item locations for different users, being initially verified before generating the trajectory for optimization purpose. However, if none of these conditions are met, a recommendation of a trajectory is made to the user. Additionally, to avoid recommendation instability, a configurable minimum time interval is considered between successive recommendation updates. Independently of the previous conditions, the recommended list of items is updated if the list becomes empty because the user has already observed all the previously recommended items. These rules ensure that an appropriate list of recommendations can be automatically kept up-to-date in a suitable way. Finally, if no more reevaluations are triggered, that path is recommended to the user.

3.2 Hospital Scenario

The use case to be studied involves an open-door visit to a hospital (e.g., for new residents or general visitors), where we would like to enhance the overall satisfaction of the users during their visit, while keeping them safe. Individuals arrive with the intent to familiarize themselves with the hospital environment,

services, and facilities, often without predetermined paths or schedules. During such events, the visitors are free to explore the hospital. The recommender system would guide them through the sprawling hospital complex, enriched with various interactive elements such as informational posters, narrative staff members ready to impart knowledge about the hospital’s history and services, and posts with educational videos.

The system’s recommendations are tailored to each visitor’s real-time location, preferences, and the current occupancy of different hospital zones, thereby ensuring a balanced flow of visitors throughout the premises. This system not only enhances the individual’s exploration experience by providing a personalized journey, but also serves the hospital institution’s goal of disseminating knowledge efficiently and maintaining a convenient level of social distance. The ultimate objective of the RS during these open-door sessions is to maximize the user satisfaction by facilitating an informative, engaging, and safe visit.

4 Experimental Evaluation

In this section, we present an experimental evaluation conducted to determine the user satisfaction during an open-doors visit to a hospital and show the benefits of the proposed location-aware recommendation approach incorporating the social distance constraints. In section 4.1, we describe the virtual environment that we use for evaluation. In Section 4.2, we describe the mixed real and synthetic dataset utilized during the experimental evaluation. Then, in Section 4.3, we present and discuss the experimental results.

4.1 Virtual Environment

The digital transformation initiative of the Hospital San Juan de Dios in Zaragoza (Spain) takes a significant leap into the metaverse with the creation of an interactive virtual hospital environment [14]. This initiative is a multidimensional web-based 3D gamified environment that is accessible through any standard web browser, enabling intuitive and exploring user experiences. Developed in collaboration with the Spanish company Imascono, this innovative digital project transforms the physical premises of the Hospital San Juan de Dios into an interactive virtual space. Figure 3 shows a screenshot of the virtual space of the Hospital San Juan de Dios [14].

The project’s aim is to transform the patient onboarding process by digitizing content, thus making patients feel more at ease and allowing them to thoroughly know the hospital, its facilities, and services. It also addresses everyday queries of users, their families, and the general public. Within this virtual space, users can discover the hospital’s innovative projects and research activities, as well as its healthcare services, current news, and social responsibility initiatives.

Interactive features such as information desks for patient services and functionalities that explain the workings of healthcare services are some of the many interactive components available within this virtual setting. Mimicking a video

Fig. 3. Virtual World Scenario of the Hospital San Juan de Dios in Zaragoza

game experience, the patient or visitor simulates entering the hospital through the digitalized hall. Once inside the virtual hospital, users encounter various interactive 3D elements, each with associated behaviors that can trigger different actions:

1. **Posters** can be interacted with through “Open”, “Click”, and “Close” actions, to display and hide information.
2. **Spheres** serve as interactive zones that users can engage with or dismiss.
3. **Screens** allow users to “Play” and “Pause” media, or expand to “FullScreen” view.
4. **NPCs (Non-Playable Characters)** can be clicked on to start or end interactions.
5. **Buttons** are clickable elements that perform specific actions within the environment.

These interactive elements were designed and visually represented to offer a clear understanding of the hospital’s virtual layout. In our work, we exploit this virtual scenario to evaluate a proposal for Side-LARS that is suitable for its real equivalent, that is a real hospital where the physical distances among users should be kept and overcrowded areas need to be avoided.

4.2 Mixed Real and Synthetic Dataset

In order to evaluate the overall satisfaction of a user during their visit in the hospital environment, we use a mixed scenario with both real and synthetic datasets. Initially, we extract relevant information from the Imascono’s Open Search database [20], which includes relevant information related to the virtual hospital environment of San Juan de Dios (see Section 4.1), such as objects (e.g., posters, screens, etc.), real-time user locations (geographic coordinates), and interactions with objects within the hospital, indicated by actions (e.g., click, close, play, pause, etc.). The resulting dataset with 12 columns and 104,056 rows,

spanning several months from early 2022 to mid-2023, comprises a rich collection of real user behaviors, object interactions, and navigation patterns, described in Table 1. We will exploit this real dataset in our experimental evaluation.

Attribute	Description	Number of unique values
timestamp	The timestamp of the recorded action, providing temporal context for each interaction.	93,237
client_id	A descriptive identifier for the client, which in this case is the Hospital San Juan de Dios.	2
object_action	Enumeration of the types of actions performed by users on objects, including comprehensive interactions like ‘Open’, ‘Close’, ‘Click’, ‘Play’, ‘Pause’, and ‘FullScreen’.	8
object_id	Either a descriptive name or a randomly generated alphanumeric code uniquely identifying each object.	34
object_type	The category of the object, with a full list that encompasses types such as ‘Player’, ‘Poster’, ‘Sphere’, ‘Screen’, ‘NPC’, and ‘Button’.	6
object_position	The geographic coordinates detailing the object’s location (X, Y, Z) within the virtual environment.	27,767
room_id	A unique identifier or descriptive name for the room of interaction.	1
user_id	A pseudonymous identifier for users, maintaining privacy while allowing behavior tracking across sessions.	19,483
vertical_id	A category or section within the virtual environment, giving context to the location and activity.	2
virtual_space_id	A descriptive identifier for different areas within the virtual environment, aiding in segmentation and analysis.	3
device_data	Details about the interaction device, including its type and operating system.	350

Table 1. Overview of the dataset attributes extracted from the virtual hospital space.

Currently, this real dataset lacks the users’ explicit interest regarding these objects. Hence, the use of AUTO-DataGenCARS+ [15], a synthetic data generator for recommender systems, could effectively bridge this gap. Initially, this tool was designed to generate recommendation datasets with explicit ratings. In order to overcome this limitation, we extended AUTO-DataGenCARS+ (see Figure 4) to generate implicit ratings based on user behaviors and pre-defined rules related with the time spent by users interacting with certain objects [6]. It should be noted that here we generate these implicit ratings synthetically, but in a real scenario we would capture/infer them using similar rules.

In Figure 5, we present the methodology carried out to generate a mixed real and synthetic dataset with implicit ratings based on user behaviors, using different AUTO-DataGenCARS+ workflows. Firstly, we extract raw data from the virtual space through the Open Search database of the Imascono Company, generating the *real_dataset.csv* file. Then, we split it into a user, item and behavior files (*user.csv*, *item.csv* and *behavior.csv*). Specifically, we use AUTO-DataGenCARS+ to generate the rating file (*rating.csv*), by using the *user.csv*, *item.csv*, *behavior.csv* files, obtained from the real dataset. In addition, we built

Fig. 4. AUTO-DataGenCARS+: Implicit Synthetic Dataset Generation Interface.

the *generation_config.conf* file, that includes setting parameters such as the minimum and maximum value of ratings (in our case, 1 and 0, indicating *like* and *dislike* respectively), a range of dates to generate the timestamps, the maximum number of rules, and the rules based on user behaviors. For example, user actions such as ‘Click’ or ‘FullScreen’ directly translate to a positive rating, while interactions with objects like ‘Posters’ and ‘Screens’ are evaluated based on the duration of engagement, with rules dictating the time thresholds for a favorable or unfavorable rating. Finally, we applied the “Extend dataset” workflow of AUTO-DataGenCARS+ to generate another dataset (*rating_extended.csv*) with a larger number of implicit ratings, by using the same files. Specifically, we expanded the real dataset by adding 100 ratings, distributed randomly in accordance with a normal distribution. The generation of these implicit ratings based on user behaviors will enable the Side-LARS model to more effectively understand the user preferences and their level of involvement in the environment. This enhancement will lead to an improved user experience, as the environment and interactions can be customized to better suit their interests. The increase in synthetic ratings will facilitate the evaluation of the RS in a larger scale.

4.3 Experimental Results

The experiments were conducted on a computer with an 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-1165G7 processor, operating at 2.80 GHz with eight cores and supported by 16 GB of RAM, running on Windows 10 Pro 64 bits and integrated graphics Intel(R) Iris(R) Xe with 8GB of RAM. The Side-LARS model operates on a server with an Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2680 v4 @ 2.40GHz processor, 377Gb RAM, and three NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080 with 8GB of RAM. Python 3.8.16 and the recommendation algorithms of the Surprise library [11] were used.

Fig. 5. Methodology applied to a mixed real and synthetic dataset with implicit ratings.

Evaluating Social Distancing Impact Through Heatmap Visualizations.

In Figure 6, we present a heatmap visualization based on the locations of users during their visits to the hospital space, using the mixed real and synthetic dataset, as detailed in Section 4.2. This map is crucial for understanding user spatial patterns and activity preferences over time. The areas are depicted using a three-color gradient, with yellow indicating zones with less traffic of people, pink highlighting the most populated areas, and an intermediate tone for areas of moderate traffic. The figure clearly shows that the highest traffic is concentrated around items (indicated by blue circular dots) close to the hospital’s main entrance. Areas depicted in intense red may suggest user dissatisfaction due to potential crowding, which could lead to a failure to maintain a safe distancing.

The proposed Side-LARS approach addresses the issue of user crowding around items, by incorporating social distancing constraints among users during the recommendation process. Initially, a user-based collaborative filtering approach is employed to recommend $k = 5$ candidate items. Specifically, we selected the KNNBaseline algorithm due to its superior performance, which is evidenced by the higher precision (0.815), recall (0.9575), and F1-score (0.864), when compared to other KNN-based recommenders (i.e., KNNBasic, KNNWith-Means, and KNNWithZScore) [11] using AUTO-DataGenCARS+. Finally, the k items recommended to users are reordered to minimize the traversed distance.

In order to evaluate the user’s satisfaction during their visit, taking social distancing into account, we conducted a one-hour Side-LARS evaluation. It was limited to 100 users with the fewest ratings in the mixed real and synthetic dataset. A significant aspect of our evaluation was the analysis of visitor distribution across the room. A balanced distribution could suggest high levels of satisfaction among visitors, while a scenario where many individuals are visiting the same item simultaneously could imply lower satisfaction. To evaluate the distribution achieved during the evaluation process, we determined the number of

Fig. 6. Hospital visit heatmap based on user locations (mixed real and synthetic dataset).

Fig. 7. Side-LARS user-item interactions map.

people interacting simultaneously with the same item. Figure 7 shows a group of users with a low density per item, being scattered throughout the different items in the room. Therefore, the Side-LARS algorithm helps in mitigating the risk of social-distance infringement between users, in turn leading to a more pleasant user experience during the visit. Overall, the experimental results demonstrate the importance of managing visitor distribution and ensuring adequate personal distance to improve user satisfaction, becoming particularly vital in scenarios where social distancing is a key consideration.

Evaluating Social Distancing Impact Through User Ratings. This experimental section aims to explore the qualitative effects of enforcing social distancing measures on user satisfaction within the context of the Side-LARS. The core hypothesis is that while social distancing is essential for safety, especially in public spaces like hospitals, it may introduce a trade-off between maintaining safety protocols and the perceived quality of the recommended systems. By integrating this additional constraint, we anticipate a potential decrease in user satisfaction regarding the recommendations provided, as this measure could limit the options available to users, possibly leading to recommendations that are less optimal from a purely personal preference standpoint. To assess the impact of social distancing on user ratings, we propose a comparative study involving two sets of recommendations: one generated by the Side-LARS algorithm with social distancing constraints and another without these constraints (pure LARS), both of them using the hybrid dataset generated from the previous experiment.

A matrix for the KNNBaseline model was computed with Pearson baseline similarity and stochastic gradient descent for baseline optimization on a dataset containing user, item, and rating information. Next, we predicted user ratings for the two different test datasets and normalized them based on a threshold (0.7) to classify them as positive or negative preferences. Afterwards, we conducted a comparative analysis by calculating the global percentage of positive and negative ratings.

Fig. 8. Comparison of User Satisfaction between SIDE-LARS and LARS

As shown in Figure 8, the implementation of SIDE-LARS, which incorporates social distancing constraints, demonstrates a marginal difference in the percentage of positive ratings when compared to the LARS algorithm without such constraints. Surprisingly, the SIDE-LARS algorithm achieved a higher percentage of positive ratings, suggesting that the additional constraint of social distancing does not necessarily lead to a decrease in user satisfaction. The results indicate that the strategic distribution of users to avoid overcrowding, as enforced by SIDE-LARS, not only supports public health measures but also contributes positively to user satisfaction. This could be attributed to users’ preference for a less crowded environment, enhancing their comfort and overall experience. Contrary to the initial hypothesis, users tend to be more satisfied with recommendations that facilitate social distancing, perhaps valuing personal space and a less congested environment over the broader range of choices.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

In this study, we tackled the challenge of combining location-based recommendations with social distancing needs, especially important in places like hospitals. Our key innovation, a Side-LARS algorithm, is all about giving users smart suggestions for where to go while keeping a safe distance from others. We put Side-LARS to the test in a realistic model of the Hospital San Juan de Dios, using a mix of real and synthetic data to check out how well it works. This let us obtain a good overview of how people move and interact in the virtual hospital, helping us make the experience better and more engaging. Our experimental evaluation demonstrates the benefits of the proposal. As far as we know, this is a relevant novelty in the literature because no other work has proposed an approach for Side-CARS or Side-LARS.

As future work, we aim to continue exploring recommendation approaches that take social distance into account, but also considering other context variables beyond the location, which would allow us to go from Side-LARS to more generic Side-CARS. We are also studying virus propagation models in order

to perform a more precise evaluation of the practical impact of our proposals. Furthermore, in-depth research could be carried out in other domains, such as tourism, with compelling potential applications.

Acknowledgments. This publication belongs to the following project: PID2020-113037RB-I00, funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033. Besides the NEAT-AMBIENCE project, we also acknowledge the Government of Aragon (COSMOS research group; last group reference: T64_23R). We thank the IMASCONO company for collaborating and providing the dataset related to the virtual space “Hospital San Juan de Dios”. This work has also been partially funded by the Department of Big Data and Cognitive Systems at the Technological Institute of Aragon, by DGA-FSE IODIDE research group of the Government of Aragon, grant number T17_23R.

References

1. Acheampong, F.A., Nunoo-Mensah, H., Chen, W.: Transformer models for text-based emotion detection: a review of BERT-based approaches. *Artificial Intelligence Review* **54**(8), 5789–5829 (2021)
2. Adomavicius, G., Tuzhilin, A.: *Context-Aware Recommender Systems*. Springer (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-85820-3>
3. Anastasiou, C., Costa, C., Chrysanthis, P.K., Shahabi, C., Zeinalipour-Yazti, D.: ASTRO: reducing covid-19 exposure through contact prediction and avoidance. *ACM Transactions on Spatial Algorithms and Systems (TSAS)* **8**(2), 1–31 (2021)
4. Baral, R., Iyengar, S.S., Li, T., Balakrishnan, N.: CLoSe: Contextualized location sequence recommender. In: *12th ACM Conference on Recommender Systems (RecSys)*. pp. 470–474. ACM (2018)
5. del Carmen Rodríguez-Hernández, M., Ilarri, S.: AI-based mobile context-aware recommender systems from an information management perspective: Progress and directions. *Knowledge-Based Systems* **215**, 1–29 (2021)
6. Esmeli, R., Bader-El-Den, M., Abdullahi, H., Henderson, D.: Implicit feedback awareness for session based recommendation in e-commerce. *SN Computer Science* **4**(3), 320 (2023)
7. Gasparetti, F., Gavalas, D., Ilarri, S., Ricci, F., Yu, Z.: Mining social networks for local search and location-based recommender systems. *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing* **23**(2), 179–180 (2019)
8. Haruna, K., Musa, A., Yunusa, Z., Ibrahim, Y., Jibia, F., Rabi, N.: Location-aware recommender system: A review of application domains and current developmental processes. *Science in Information Technology Letters* **2**(1), 28–42 (2022)
9. Ho, N.L., Lee, R.K.W., Lim, K.H.: BTRec: BERT-based trajectory recommendation for personalized tours. *arXiv* pp. 1–9 (2023)
10. Ho, N.L., Lim, K.H.: POIBERT: A transformer-based model for the tour recommendation problem. In: *2022 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data)*. pp. 5925–5933. IEEE (2022)
11. Hug, N.: Surprise, a Python library for recommender systems (2017), <http://surpriselib.com>, [Accessed on April 6, 2024]
12. Ilarri, S., Trillo-Lado, R., Ángel Arraez, Piedrafita, A.: Simulating scenarios to evaluate data filtering techniques for mobile users. In: *20th International Conference on Advances in Mobile Computing & Multimedia (MoMM)*. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS)*, vol. 13634, pp. 87–101. Springer (2022)

13. Ilarri, S., Trillo-Lado, R., Delot, T.: Social-distance aware data management for mobile computing. In: 18th International Conference on Advances in Mobile Computing & Multimedia (MoMM). pp. 138–142. ACM (2021)
14. Imascono: Hospital virtual San Juan de Dios, Zaragoza. <https://virtual.hsjdzaragoza.es> (2023), [Accessed on April 6, 2024]
15. ITAINNOVA, Universidad de Zaragoza: AUTO-DataGenCARS+: Python-Based Advanced User oriented tOol DataGenCARS. <http://webdiis.unizar.es/~silarri/prot/AUTO-DataGenCARSPPlus/> (2022–2024), last access: December 8, 2023.
16. Lian, D., Wu, Y., Ge, Y., Xie, X., Chen, E.: Geography-aware sequential location recommendation. In: 26th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery & Data Mining (KDD). pp. 2009–2019. ACM (2020)
17. Liu, J., Wood, K.L., Lim, K.H.: Strategic and crowd-aware itinerary recommendation. In: Dong, Y., Mladenić, D., Saunders, C. (eds.) Machine Learning and Knowledge Discovery in Databases: Applied Data Science Track (ECML PKDD). Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS), vol. 12460, pp. 69–85. Springer (2021)
18. Meng, X., Du, Y., Zhang, Y., Han, X.: A survey of context-aware recommender systems: From an evaluation perspective. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* **35**(7), 6575–6594 (2023)
19. Noorian, A., Harounabadi, A., Hazratifard, M.: A sequential neural recommendation system exploiting BERT and LSTM on social media posts. *Complex & Intelligent Systems* pp. 1–24 (2023)
20. Open Search Project: Open search 2.13.0. <https://github.com/opensearch-project/OpenSearch> (2021), accessed on April 6, 2024
21. Pelleg, D., Moore, A.W.: X-Means: Extending K-Means with efficient estimation of the number of clusters. In: 7th International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML). vol. 1, pp. 727–734. Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc. (2000)
22. Rodríguez Hernández, M.d.C., Ilarri Artigas, S., Trillo, R., Hermoso, R.: Context-aware recommendations using mobile P2P. In: 15th International Conference on Advances in Mobile Computing & Multimedia (MoMM). pp. 82–91. ACM (2017)
23. Sánchez, P., Bellogín, A.: Point-of-interest recommender systems based on location-based social networks: A survey from an experimental perspective. *ACM Computing Surveys* **54**(11s), 1–37 (2022)
24. Sarris, V.E., Chrysanthis, P.K., Costa, C.: Recommending the least congested indoor-outdoor paths without ignoring time. In: Proceedings of the 18th International Symposium on Spatial and Temporal Data. pp. 121–130. Association for Computing Machinery (2023)
25. Schubert, E., Sander, J., Ester, M., Kriegel, H.P., Xu, X.: DBSCAN revisited, revisited: why and how you should (still) use DBSCAN. *ACM Transactions on Database Systems* **42**(3), 1–21 (2017)
26. Zhou, J., Gu, Y., Lin, W.: Complementing travel itinerary recommendation using location-based social networks. In: Fifth IEEE International Conference on Internet of People (IoP). pp. 1876–1881. IEEE (2019)